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Ancient gates of Bukhara.

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Annotatsiya: This article contains information about the historical gates of the city of Bukhara. The locations and names of the ancient gates are explained.

Keywords: Gates of Bukhara, Registan, Allafurishan, Haqroh (Khurfa), Attoron, Nav, Kuhandiz, Muhra, Bani Sad.

The city of Bukhara is one of the oldest cities of our country, the city was built on the basis of the traditions of medieval urbanism. In the early Middle Ages, there were 2 gates in the city arch: the Western gate was called Registan, Allafurishan or Somonfuusan, and the Eastern gate was called Gorayon.

There were 7 gates on 4 sides of Shahrsto

- Haqroh (Khurfa) in the north

- Attoron (Babylon Medina) Ohaniyan

(Blacksmiths) in the south

- Light in the East

- there were Kuhandiz, Muhra (Bani Asad)

and Bani Sad gates in the west.

In the past 23 years after the independence of Uzbekistan, in all aspects of the economic and social life of our country, including our region,

including preserving the historical monuments inherited from our ancestors, renovating them and presenting them to future generations. For centuries, great works have been done in terms of delivery.

In particular, as part of the preparations for the 2500th anniversary of Bukhara and its implementation based on the decision of President I. Karimov, Kalon architectural complex, Mir-Arab, Ulugbek madrasas, Ark fortress, Samonii mausoleum, Labihovuz complex and many other monuments were restored. The shrines of Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani, Bahauddin Naqshband, Sayyid Mir Kulol and other Sufi scholars were rebuilt, and the architectural complex of Chorbakr, which had fallen into disrepair due to centuries of neglect, was rebuilt.

The ancient fortress surrounding Bukharai Sharif and its gates have been an integral part of the urban planning and architecture of this ancient land for centuries. However, during the invasion of Bukhara by the Red Army in the fall of 1920, the city's fortress and gates were fired from cannons and bombarded, national values and traditions were completely ignored in socialist urban development, and the state did not pay attention to the maintenance of the monuments of our country. Due to the insufficient amount of funds allocated from the budget, only a few tens of meters of the 12-kilometer-long fortress and only 2 of the ancient gates are left, which may lead to the disappearance of the unique architectural image of this old land. Taking this into account, regional governor S. Husenov initiated a good project to rebuild a part of the ancient fortress and the city gates with the support of a group of dignified patrons, talented architects and repairmen. .

The materials published on page 3 of our newspaper are devoted to the results of scientific and creative research and hard work carried out in this direction.

Bukhara fortress walls and gates

A group of repair masters led by the laureate of the State Prize of the Republic of Uzbekistan Olim Abdiyev (in the photo) rebuilt this magnificent monument in 2009 on the basis of the project of architect Mahmud Akhmedov on the foundation of the Samarkand Gate, which was built in the 16th century by the ruler of Bukhara Abdulaziz Khan on the banks of the Great Silk Road. made it.

Literature:

1. Gapparov, A. (2023). DIACHRONIC ANALYSIS OF SOCIO-POLITICAL VOCABULARY. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(4 Part 3), 140-147.
2. Gapparov, A. (2023). DIACHRONIC ANALYSIS OF SOCIO-POLITICAL VOCABULARY. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(4 Part 3), 140-147.
3. Shamsikamar, A., & Ziyodullayevna, M. B. (2022). Interiors of Historic Hospitals. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 2(5), 227-229.
4. Shamsikamar, A. (2021). Historical architectural rules when designing buildings. *Journal of Architectural Design*, 1, 6-9.
5. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Palaces of the Timurid Period of the middle Ages of Uzbekistan. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, 2(2), 24-28.
6. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2022). Palaces In The Historical Cities Of Uzbekistan Formation. *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12, 15-18.

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VOLUME-3, ISSUE-4

7. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Analytical Research Work on the Palaces of the Timurids in the Medieval Period of Uzbekistan. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 4(3), 7-10.
8. Sabohat, M., & Firuza, M. (2022). Periods of Formation of Historical Structures of Architecture with Geometric Shapes. *Journal of Architectural Design*, 4, 21-26.
9. Ibraimovna, M. F. Abdusattorovna, M. S. (2023). Analytical Research Work on the Palaces of the Timurids in the Medieval Period of Uzbekistan. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 4(3), 7-10.
10. Firuza Ibraimovna, M. (2023). Scientific and Natural Study of the Architecture of the Khiva Garden-Palaces, Development of Recommendations for their Use for Modern Tourism Purposes. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education*, 2(3), 10-13.
11. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Analysis of Various Roofs and Roofs. *Nexus: Journal of Advances Studies of Engineering Science*, 2(3), 33-39.
12. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Khiva is an Open-Air City-Museum. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, 2(4), 36-39.
13. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). History of Khiva. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, 2(4), 8-12.
14. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Experiences of Restoring Palaces in Historical Cities of Uzbekistan and Historical Parks Around Them. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, 2(3), 41-44.
15. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Formation of Palaces in Uzbekistan in the Late Middle Ages-Khanate Period. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, 2(3), 33-36.
16. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(5), 10-14.
17. Makhmudova, F. (2023). DEPARTMENT OF ARCHITECTURE. STUDY AND CALCULATION OF SPATIAL BLOCKS WITH A CYLINDRICAL COATING SHELL. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(10), 163-166.